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Financial Development, Energy Use and Urbanization on Ecological Footprints in OIC Economies: Heterogeneous Effects Assessment

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Abstract

Environmental sustainability and the maintenance of a clean, healthy ecosystem have become critical global concerns, attracting significant attention from many nations. This study investigates the heterogeneous effects of financial development, energy consumption, and urbanization on the ecological footprint within a panel of 37 economies in the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) over a 25-year period (2000-2024). Employing dynamic panel quantile regression, the empirical results indicate that financial development significantly reduces the ecological footprint. In contrast, urbanization exerts a statistically significant adverse effect on the ecological footprint in OIC countries, while the impact of energy consumption varies across quantiles. Therefore, institutionalizing green financial development as a priority policy incorporating environmental standards into financial regulations and credit allocation is recommended for OIC countries. Additionally, sustainable urban development strategies, such as investment in smart city technologies and effective waste management, should be implemented. Energy consumption policies should also be tailored to the specific circumstances of each OIC nation.

Keywords: Financial Development, Ecological Footprint, Energy Use, Urbanization, Dynamic panel quantile regression, OIC countries

JEL Classifications: Q5, G20, Q43, O18

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Introduction

The pursuit of economic development remains a global aspiration, yet it is increasingly challenged by the imperative of environmental sustainability (Bekun et al., 2024; Destek and Sarkodie, 2019). Human-induced environmental degradation continues to escalate, primarily driven by industrialization, consumption, and population growth (Ahmad et al., 2018; Shahbaz et al., 2013). Addressing this issue necessitates the adoption of comprehensive and quantifiable measures to assess the true extent of human demand on natural systems.

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The Ecological Footprint (EF) has emerged as a widely recognized indicator of human impact on the environment (Destek and Sarkodie, 2019; Wachernagel and Rees, 1998). EF quantifies the biologically productive land and sea area required to generate the resources consumed by a population and to assimilate the resulting waste, predominantly carbon emissions, typically measured in global hectares (gha) per capita (Galli et al., 2012). This metric provides a direct comparison between humanity's demand and the Earth's regenerative capacity, known as biocapacity, highlighting instances of unsustainable ecological deficits (Wachernagel and Rees, 1998; Zafar et al., 2019). In most countries, energy-related emissions constitute the largest component of the ecological footprint, with the carbon footprint being predominant (Zafar et al., 2019). The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) is a diverse coalition of 57 member states, encompassing a wide range of developmental stages, resource endowments, and institutional frameworks (Bekun et al., 2024; Muhammad, 2019). Most OIC economies are classified as emerging or developing, characterized by high urbanization rates, rapid population growth, and significant reliance on energy-intensive sectors to drive economic growth (Ahmad et al., 2018; Muhammad, 2019). Consequently, these developmental trajectories are frequently associated with heightened environmental stress and an expanding ecological footprint (Khan et al., 2020; Zoundi, 2017).

The situation within the OIC is particularly salient, as member states must balance economic development objectives with the principles of sustainable development and the ethical imperatives of Islamic doctrine, which emphasize resource stewardship and environmental protection (Destek and Sarkodie, 2019; Shahbaz et al., 2013). Understanding the drivers of the ecological footprint in these countries is essential for formulating effective, context-specific policies to facilitate a transition toward a green economy (Bekun et al., 2024; Khan et al., 2020). Empirical evidence indicates that the primary determinants of the ecological footprint are a combination of macroeconomic and demographic factors, specifically financial development, energy consumption, and urbanization (Destek and Sarkodie, 2019; Iftikhar Yasin et al., 2020). However, the relationships among these factors are complex and often contradictory within the unique socioeconomic and regulatory context of OIC economies. The efficiency and depth of a country's financial markets and institutions exhibit a dual association with environmental quality (Tamazian and Rao, 2010). On one hand, a well-developed financial sector can increase the ecological footprint by facilitating access to credit, thereby promoting consumption, industrial investment, and aggregate energy use (Sadorsky, 2010; Zhang et al., 2022).

This expansionary scale effect encourages carbon-intensive activities in emerging economies, including OIC member states (Acheampong, 2019; R. Wang et al., 2020). Conversely, the technology or composition effect can reduce the ecological footprint by enabling investments in cleaner, energy-efficient technologies and promoting the development of renewable energy resources, such as Green Sukuk and advanced renewables (Zhang, 2011; Shahbaz et al., 2013). However, empirical findings regarding OIC countries and other regions are inconsistent. Some studies suggest that financial development exacerbates environmental degradation (Boutabba, 2014), while others indicate that deeper financial systems can mitigate pollution and improve the ecological footprint (Elmonshid et al., 2024; Khan et al., 2022). Energy consumption is widely recognized as the most direct and significant contributor to the ecological footprint, particularly its carbon component (Rehan et al., 2025). The heavy reliance on non-renewable energy sources, such as fossil fuels, to meet the growing energy demands of developing and emerging OIC economies directly increases greenhouse gas emissions and environmental degradation (Gyamfi et al., 2024; Ocal and Aslan, 2013). Numerous studies across various regions confirm a strong positive correlation between energy use and the ecological footprint, underscoring the importance of energy policy (Muhammad, 2019; Zhang et al., 2017).

The type of energy source is also significant: increased reliance on fossil fuels exacerbates the ecological footprint, whereas greater adoption of renewable energy demonstrates a strong mitigating effect (Chen et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2022). Urbanization, defined by a rising proportion of the population residing in cities, represents a dynamic environmental challenge for OIC countries experiencing rapid urban transformation (Rashid et al., 2018). While concentrated urban settlements could theoretically enhance the efficiency of infrastructure and service use, the predominant effect in most developing contexts is negative (Ahmad et al., 2019; Ulucak and Erdem, 2017). Urban population growth drives higher demand for energy-intensive buildings, transportation, and consumer goods, thereby increasing per capita ecological footprint (Ahmad et al., 2019; Iftikhar Yasin et al., 2020). Although some studies suggest complex or even negative long-term relationships between urbanization and ecological footprint, the majority of literature concerning developing and OIC countries identifies urbanization as a significant and persistent factor contributing to environmental degradation (Iftikhar Yasin et al., 2020; Ulucak and Apergis, 2018). Given these intricate and sometimes contradictory dynamics, OIC economies necessitate targeted and nuanced analysis.

The literature consistently highlights that while economic development is vital, it is frequently associated with an increased ecological footprint. Financial development, energy consumption, and urbanization are identified as key determinants shaping sustainability trajectories (Bekun et al., 2024; Destek and Sarkodie, 2019). Accordingly, this study aims to comprehensively assess both the collective and individual impacts of financial development, energy consumption, and urbanization on the ecological footprint within the specific institutional and economic context of the OIC bloc. The resulting empirical evidence will inform sustainable development policy in these countries. The contributions of this research are as follows: (1) it addresses the understudied nexus between financial development, energy consumption, and urbanization in relation to ecological footprints within OIC economies, thereby filling a significant research gap; (2) it employs dynamic panel quantile regression with non-additive fixed effects, as developed by Powell (2016), to address endogeneity and simultaneity concerns. This methodological approach has not previously been applied to analyze the relationship among these variables in the OIC context. The technique estimates conditional quantile functions for the dependent variables and accounts for specification errors due to outliers. The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature; Section 3 details the model specification and econometric methodology; Section 4 presents the empirical findings; and the final section concludes with findings and policy implications.

Literature Review

The empirical literature demonstrates a growing interest in examining the environmental implications of economic growth, financial development, energy consumption, and other macroeconomic variables through the frameworks of the Ecological Footprint (EF) and Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypotheses. Most studies utilize time-series (e.g. Makhdum et al., 2022; Solarin et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2021; Usman et al., 2020) or panel data econometric methods (see Adow et al., 2025; Ahmad et al., 2022; Nathaniel et al., 2021; Ozturk et al., 2015), including ARDL, FMOLS, DOLS, GMM, AMG, CCEMG, and cointegration techniques. These approaches are widely adopted to capture both short- and long-run dynamics of environmental degradation across diverse economic contexts. The EKC hypothesis is supported by a significant proportion of studies, such as Nathaniel et al. (2021), Destek and Sinha (2020), Al-Mulali et al. (2015), and Makhdum et al. (2022), which find that environmental degradation initially rises with economic growth but subsequently declines after reaching a certain income threshold. However, this pattern is not universal; Foo et al. (2019) and Ahmed et al. (2020) identify a U-shaped or monotonic relationship, indicating that environmental degradation may persist or even worsen despite increasing income. Additionally, financial development emerges as a complex, dual-faceted factor within these economies.

Empirical studies by Ahmad et al. (2022) and Makhdum et al. (2022) indicate that while well-directed financial development can stimulate green investment, it may also increase the ecological footprint if funds are allocated to polluting industries. Human capital has consistently been found to mitigate environmental deterioration (Ahmad et al., 2022; Rafique et al., 2022; Zia et al., 2021). Education, skills, and environmental awareness play significant roles in fostering sustainable practices. Several studies identify energy consumption, particularly non-renewable energy use (e.g., Mujtaba et al., 2022; Sarkodie and Owusu, 2021; Usman et al., 2020; Destek and Dogan, 2018), as the primary driver of environmental degradation. Conversely, the adoption of renewable energy and improvements in institutional quality (Makhdum et al., 2022) are associated with reduced ecological harm, underscoring the necessity of a clean energy transition. The impacts of urbanization, trade openness, and globalization are heterogeneous: in some contexts (e.g., Solarin et al., 2021; Foo et al., 2019), urbanization enhances environmental quality, while in others (Ahmad et al., 2022; Karsuh and Erkut, 2022), it contributes to a larger ecological footprint. These variations are typically attributed to differences in urban planning, technological adaptation, and policy enforcement. Furthermore, studies focusing on developing and emerging economies (e.g., China, Nigeria, Pakistan, Thailand, Japan, BRICST) highlight that the trade-offs between economic growth and sustainability persist.

The results reported in the literature are often case-specific and context-dependent, limiting their generalizability. Panel data studies (e.g., Rafique et al., 2022; Usman et al., 2020; Al-Mulali et al., 2015) highlight heterogeneity across income groups and demonstrate that environmental outcomes are significantly influenced by economic structure, institutional strength, and regional policies. Most existing research focuses on Asia, BRICS, OECD countries, and the MENA bloc, while OIC countries receive comparatively little attention. Due to the unique institutional backgrounds and developmental contexts of OIC economies, findings from Asia, OECD, and other regions may not be directly applicable. Furthermore, while several studies examine traditional predictors such as trade, economic growth, and energy, the role of financial development in influencing ecological footprint remains largely understudied in the empirical literature. Therefore, it is essential to conduct research that addresses the specific context of OIC states regarding ecological footprint to bridge these gaps, which constitutes the primary objective of this study. Table 1 below summarizes the empirical findings reviewed.

Author(s) & date	Period of Coverage	Method of Analysis	Variables	Key Findings
Ahmad <i>et al.</i> 2022	1990–2018 (BRICST)	Panel Quantile Regression	Financial development, human capital, urbanization, economic growth, energy use	Financial development and urbanization worsen ecological footprint; human capital mitigates it
Kongbuamai <i>et al.</i> 2020	1974–2016 (Thailand)	ARDL	Economic growth, energy use, tourism, trade openness, ecological footprint	Economic growth, energy use, and trade openness increase ecological footprint; tourism and population reduce it
Ahmed <i>et al.</i> 2021	– (Japan)	ARDL (symmetric & asymmetric)	Ecological footprint, globalization, economic growth, financial development, population density, energy use	Long-run relationship between ecological footprint and globalization, financial development, and growth
Nathaniel <i>et al.</i> 2021	1990–2016 (11 countries)	Cross-sectional dependence, CADF, CIPS, Westerlund cointegration, AMG, CCEMG, DK	Economic growth, energy use, trade, environmental regulation, ecological footprint	EKC hypothesis validated (inverted U-shape); energy use & trade worsen environment; weak regulations
Menghwani <i>et al.</i> 2019	2016–2018 (India)	Randomized Controlled Trial; Logistic & Multinomial Regression	Wealth, caste, education, gender, stove pricing, dissemination	Wealth and education predict clean fuel use; female empowerment improves adoption
Destek <i>et al.</i> 2018.	1980–2013 (15 EU)	Second-generation panel: CIPS, FMOLS, DOLS, DCCE	Ecological footprint, GDP, GDP ² , renewable/non-renewable energy, trade openness	EKC partially valid; renewable energy reduces footprint, non-renewable increases
Imran <i>et al.</i> 2019	Late 2010s (Pakistan)	Multivariate Probit Model	Education, income, land size, household size, fuel types	Income, education, and awareness drive cleaner energy use
Usman <i>et al.</i> 2020.	1994–2017 (33 countries)	FMOLS, DOLS, FGLS, AMG, Dumitrescu-Hurlin causality	GDP, FDI, energy, trade, ecological footprint	Region-specific effects; renewable energy reduces footprint; trade & growth effects vary
Ahmed <i>et al.</i> 2020	1970–2016 (China)	Bayer–Hanck cointegration, ARDL, Bootstrap causality	Natural resources, human capital, urbanization, economic growth	Resources & urbanization worsen environment; human capital mitigates; EKC not confirmed
Destek & Sinha, 2020	1980–2014 (OECD)	Cross-sectional dependence, Westerlund cointegration, DOLS, FMOLS	Renewable & non-renewable energy, GDP, trade openness, ecological footprint	Renewable energy improves, non-renewable worsens environment; partial EKC
Usman <i>et al.</i> 2020.	1971–2014 (South Africa)	ARDL bounds, Toda-Yamamoto causality	Energy use, trade, globalization, CO ₂ emissions	Energy & globalization raise CO ₂ ; trade effect insignificant
Foo <i>et al.</i> 2019.	1978–2013 (Malaysia)	ARDL & Granger causality	GDP, financial liberalization, trade, energy, urbanization	GDP & energy harm environment; urbanization improves it; EKC rejected (U-shape)

Author(s) & date	Period of Coverage	Method of Analysis	Variables	Key Findings
Foo <i>et al.</i> 2019	1978–2013 (Malaysia)	ARDL & Granger causality	GDP, financial liberalization, trade, energy, urbanization	GDP & energy harm environment; urbanization improves it; EKC rejected (U-shape)
Makhdum <i>et al.</i> 2022	1996–2020 (China)	ARDL, Johansen cointegration, Granger causality	Institutional quality, natural resources, renewable energy, financial development	Institutional quality & renewables reduce footprint; resources & finance increase it
Solarin <i>et al.</i> 2021	1977–2016 (Nigeria)	Dynamic ARDL, Bayer–Hanck cointegration	GDP, urbanization, trade, FDI, ecological footprint	Short-run: growth, trade & FDI degrade environment; long-run: growth & urbanization improve it
Al-Mulali <i>et al.</i> 2015	1980–2008 (93 countries)	Fixed effects & GMM	GDP, GDP ² , energy, trade, urbanization, financial development	EKC holds for high-income countries; energy & urbanization worsen footprint
Zia <i>et al.</i> 2021	1985–2018 (China)	Dynamic Simulated ARDL	Natural resources, human capital, financial development, GDP, ecological footprint	Growth, resources & finance increase footprint; EKC valid in long-run
Rafique <i>et al.</i> 2022	1980–2017 (Top 10 economies)	FMOLS, DOLS, System GMM	Economic complexity, human capital, renewable energy, urbanization, GDP, trade	Trade, GDP, and urbanization worsen footprint; human capital & renewables improve
Adow <i>et al.</i> 2025	1990–2022 (6 GCC)	Panel Cross-sectional Dependence, Threshold Tests	Energy use, financial development, urbanization, CO ₂ , income	EKC holds; financial development reduces emissions; energy use & urbanization increase it
Mujtaba <i>et al.</i> 2022	1971–2014 (5 regions)	Panel Nonlinear ARDL (PNARDL)	GDP, energy, population, CO ₂ emissions	Energy & population increase emissions; non-symmetrical GDP impacts across regions
Sarkodie & Owusu 2021	1990–2018 (MENA)	Panel unit root, AMG, CCEMG	GDP, energy demand, urbanization, globalization, CO ₂	Growth, energy, and urbanization increase CO ₂ ; mixed globalization effect
Charfeddine 2017	1970–2015 (Qatar)	Markov Switching ECM	GDP, energy, trade, urbanization, finance, ecological footprint	EKC valid; trade & urbanization worsen footprint; finance reduces it
Ozturk <i>et al.</i> 2015	1988–2008 (144 countries)	GMM & System GMM	GDP, tourism, trade, energy, urbanization	EKC supported for high-income; tourism drives footprint; trade & energy effects mixed
Udemba 2020	1981–2018 (Nigeria)	ARDL, Granger causality	GDP, FDI, agriculture, energy, population	Economic growth and FDI increase footprint; EKC scale effect stage
Khan <i>et al.</i> 2019	1990–2016 (5 BRI blocs)	AMG, CCEMG, Heterogeneous causality	GDP, energy, financial dev., FDI, ecological footprint	Confirms pollution haven, EKC, energy & finance push emission hypotheses

Empirical model and the data

Empirical model

The present study employs an econometric technique consistent with the approaches of Shuaibu and Law (2025), Sarkodie and Strezov (2019), and Aldieri and Vinci (2017) to evaluate the relationship between ecological footprint and a set of regressors in OIC countries. Specifically, the dynamic quantile regression for panel data with non-additive fixed effects, as proposed by Powell (2016), is utilized. This method addresses challenges associated with quantile regression with fixed effects and other mean estimators, such as random and fixed effects. Dynamic panel quantile regression is preferred due to its reduced sensitivity to outliers and its ability to capture the full conditional distribution of the dependent variable (ECF) across different quantiles. The Koenker and Bassett (1978) quantile model is presented below:

$$ECF_i = X_i \beta_\tau + \mu_i$$

(1)

where ECF is the dependent variable, X represents the vector of explanatory variables, β denotes the vector of coefficients to be estimated, and μ is the disturbance terms. The equation (1) above is transformed into the following:

$$LNECF_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 LNECF_{it-1} + \alpha_2 LNFD_{it} + \alpha_3 LNURB_{it} + \alpha_4 LNEU_{it} + \alpha_5 LN. \\ \alpha_6 LNFDI_{it} + \alpha_7 LNTTO_{it} + \eta_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

(2)

In this context, i denotes the country subscript and t represents the time subscript. ECF indicates the ecological footprint, FD denotes financial development, URB refers to the urban population, EU signifies energy use, RGDP stands for real gross domestic product, FDI represents foreign direct investment, and TO refers to trade openness. The term η_i captures country-specific effects, ε is the disturbance term, and α s are parameters to be estimated. All variables are expressed in logarithmic form, allowing the coefficients to be interpreted as elasticities and mitigating the influence of outliers.

The Data

This study employs panel data from 37 member countries of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, covering the period from 2000 to 2024. The selection of countries and variables is guided by data availability and prior empirical research (see Ahmad et al., 2022; Ahmed et al., 2021; Usman et al., 2020). The ecological footprint data are obtained from the Global Footprint Network, while other variables, including financial development, energy use, urbanization, foreign direct investment, real economic growth, and trade openness, are sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI)..

Table 1:

Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Ecological footprint (ef)	925	4.69000	7.11000	7.97070	3.48000
Financial development (fd)	925	33.7694	27.4515	1.26604	138.420
Energy use (eu)	925	2592.04	3916.97	112.880	21557.5
Urbanization (urb)	925	1.760007	2.64000	2.32296	1.70000
Real GDP (rgdp)	925	9110.55	14251.1	287.391	81608.6
Foreign direct investment (fdi)	925	2555.99	4956.30	-10176.0	46578.0
Trade openness (to)	925	74.5889	36.1269	2.46152	220.407

Descriptive statistics

Table 2

Variable	LEF	LFD	LURB	LEU	LFDI	LRGDP	LTO
LEF	1.0000						
LFD	-0.2586	1.0000					
LURB	0.6471	0.1300	1.0000				
LEU	-0.2927	0.5223	-0.2102	1.0000			
LFDI	0.2783	0.4728	0.5155	0.3432	1.0000		
LRGDP	-0.3217	0.6001	-0.1474	0.9533	0.4113	1.0000	
LTO	-0.4315	0.4437	-0.4182	0.5304	0.1206	0.5029	1.0000

Correlation matrix

NB. All the variables are transformed into natural logarithms. Pearson correlation coefficient ranges between ± 1 indicates strong or weak linear association.

The ecological footprint, financial development, energy use, urbanization, etc. mean values and standard deviation as depicted in table 1 suggest significant heterogeneity across the economies in OIC. These variations are largely due to the level of environmental pressure in areas such as pattern of consumption, economic structure, size of population, etc. while table 2 presents the correlation matrix that shows the relationships between ecological footprint (lef), financial development (lfd), urbanization (lurb), energy consumption (leu), foreign direct investment (lfdi), real GDP (lrgdp) and trade openness (lto). The findings in general show moderate to strong correlations where most of the results are in line with theories. Notably, some of the variables are highly correlated, especially between the energy use and the real GDP.

The table 3 depicts the results of mean or static estimators. Whereas the table 4 presents the dynamic panel quantile regression (QR) estimates of the determinants of the logarithm of ecological footprint (LEF) across nine quantiles (0.1 to 0.9). The results include coefficients for lagged logarithm of ecological footprint (LAGEF), financial development (LFD), urbanization (LURB), energy use (LEU), foreign direct investment (LFDI), real GDP (LRGDP), and trade openness (LTO). The analysis covers 835 observations from 37 countries. The lagged dependent variable (LAGEF) is statistically significant at 1% across all the quantiles estimated, which reflect a strong persistence of ecological footprint over time. This result indicates that previous levels of ecological footprint in OIC countries are highly predictive of current values, which is in line with environmental inertia and path dependency in ecological degradation.

Table 3

VARIABLES	Pooled OLS	Random effect	Fixed effect
LAGEF	0.999*** (0.000495)	0.999*** (0.000509)	0.885*** (0.0151)
LFD	-0.000295 (0.000885)	-0.000301 (0.000899)	-0.00305* (0.00157)
LURB	0.000783 (0.000665)	0.000789 (0.000681)	0.00360 (0.00262)
LEU	-0.00110 (0.00143)	-0.00103 (0.00147)	0.00348 (0.00435)
LFDI	-0.000463 (0.000475)	-0.000466 (0.000479)	-0.000204 (0.000577)
LRGDP	0.000493 (0.00143)	0.000443 (0.00147)	0.00404 (0.00360)
LTO	0.00145 (0.00135)	0.00137 (0.00137)	0.00248 (0.00230)
Constant	0.00745 (0.0122)	0.00789 (0.0125)	1.805*** (0.244)
Observations	835	835	835
R-squared	1.000		0.843
Number of code		37	37

The Results of Static Panel Data Analysis; Dependent Variable: LOGEF

Notes: LAGEF = Ecological Footprint LFD = Log Financial Development, LURB = Log Urbanization, LEU = Log Energy Use, LFDI = Log Foreign Direct Investment, LRGDP = Log Real GDP and LTO = Trade Openness. Standard errors are in parentheses ***, ** and * denote significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

Financial Development (LFD), coefficients are negative and statistically significant at all quantiles. This implies that higher financial development is attributed to a reduction in ecological footprint, particularly in lower to middle quantiles, suggesting that financial sector maturity enhances and facilitates investment in environmentally friendly ecosystems/technologies and efficient use of resource. This empirical finding is in line with Adow, et al 2025 as opposed to Ahmad, et al 2022. However, the effect decreases slightly at higher quantiles (Q0.8-Q0.9), depicting that in economies that are already associated with high ecological footprints, additional financial development has a somewhat smaller mitigating effect. Urbanization (LURB) has positive and highly significant coefficients across all quantiles; this demonstrates that the

Table 4: The result of dynamic panel quantile regression estimations. Dependent variable: Log of Ecological footprint (N=37 countries, T= 25; sample period = 2000-2024)

VARIABLES	QRPD0.1	QRPD0.2	QRPD0.3	QRPD0.4	QRPD0.5	QRPD0.6	QRPD0.7	QRPD0.8	QRPD0.9
LAGEF	1.000*** (4.62e-05)	1.000*** (2.22e-05)	0.999*** (2.45e-05)	1.000*** (5.45e-05)	0.999*** (1.80e-05)	0.999*** (7.73e-06)	0.999*** (6.22e-06)	0.999*** (7.19e-06)	0.999*** (6.04e-06)
LFD	-0.000177*** (4.98e-05)	-0.000182*** (4.00e-05)	-0.000449*** (3.64e-05)	-0.00107*** (5.77e-05)	-0.000681*** (3.58e-05)	-0.000474*** (5.50e-05)	-0.000376*** (2.44e-05)	-0.000325*** (1.72e-05)	-0.000451*** (1.40e-05)
LURB	0.000518*** (7.34e-05)	0.000608*** (3.05e-05)	0.000645*** (1.98e-05)	0.000688*** (5.23e-05)	0.000761*** (3.73e-05)	0.000555*** (3.63e-05)	0.000555*** (1.08e-05)	0.000540*** (7.88e-06)	0.000533*** (7.52e-06)
LEU	4.30e-05 (7.74e-05)	-3.63e-05 (4.64e-05)	-0.000151 (9.72e-05)	-0.000223** (9.76e-05)	4.96e-05 (7.12e-05)	0.000489*** (4.95e-05)	0.000619*** (4.12e-05)	0.000629*** (2.58e-05)	0.000291*** (3.93e-05)
LFDI	6.99e-07 (2.77e-05)	1.98e-05 (2.77e-05)	-1.91e-05 (2.04e-05)	-2.55e-05 (2.02e-05)	-2.12e-05*** (8.06e-06)	1.00e-05 (1.40e-05)	2.27e-05*** (7.47e-06)	1.75e-05** (8.48e-06)	1.03e-05* (5.79e-06)
LRGDP	-0.000277*** (5.76e-05)	-0.000211*** (3.29e-05)	-0.000140** (6.58e-05)	0.000359*** (9.19e-05)	-1.39e-05 (7.46e-05)	-0.000429*** (5.40e-05)	-0.000562*** (3.95e-05)	-0.000601*** (2.31e-05)	-0.000253*** (2.72e-05)
LTO	5.70e-06 (0.000116)	-9.62e-05 (0.000137)	2.55e-05 (4.77e-05)	0.000363*** (4.63e-05)	0.000158*** (4.26e-05)	-0.000114** (5.33e-05)	-0.000128*** (2.48e-05)	-4.75e-05** (2.27e-05)	-8.77e-05*** (2.48e-05)
Observations	835	835	835	835	835	835	835	835	835
Number of groups	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37	37

Notes: LAGEF =Ecological Footprint LFD = Log Financial Development, LURB = Log Urbanization, LEU = Log Energy Use, LFDI= Log Foreign Direct Investment, LRGDP = Log Real GDP and LTO = Trade Openness. Standard errors are in parentheses ***, ** and * denote significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively.

An increased urban population contributes to higher ecological footprints, aligning with empirical findings that urban concentration elevates energy demand, waste production, and resource consumption (see Adow et al., 2025; Rafique et al., 2022; Sarkodie et al., 2021). The effect is marginally stronger in the mid-quantiles, such as Q0.4 and Q0.5, indicating that urbanization exerts the greatest marginal influence on ecological footprint in countries experiencing moderate levels of environmental pressure. Energy use (LEU) demonstrates heterogeneous effects across the estimated quantiles. For quantiles 0.1 to 0.3, the impact of energy use on ecological footprint is not statistically significant. At quantile 0.4, the influence is negative and statistically significant at the 5% level, while quantiles 0.6 and 0.8 display positive and significant effects. These results indicate that the environmental impact of energy consumption is nonlinear. In countries with lower ecological footprints, energy use has a minimal effect, whereas in countries with mid-to-high ecological footprints, increased energy consumption significantly intensifies ecological pressure (Adow et al., 2025; Karsuh and Erkut, 2022; Mujtaba et al., 2022; Usman et al., 2020). This variation may be attributed to differences in energy mix, efficiency, and regulatory frameworks.

The effect of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) varies across the estimated quantiles. FDI is statistically insignificant at lower and middle quantiles, negative and statistically significant at the 1% level in quantile Q0.5, and positive and significant at higher quantiles (Q0.7–Q0.9). This suggests that FDI can either mitigate ecological footprint through green investment or exacerbate it via the potential pollution haven effect (see Udemba, 2020). The variation in sign across quantiles underscores the heterogeneous impact of FDI, which depends on the level of environmental pressure. Real GDP (LRGDP) exhibits mostly negative and significant coefficients at most quantiles, except for Q0.4, which is positive and statistically significant, and Q0.5, which is insignificant. Overall, economic growth appears to mitigate ecological footprint in OIC countries, indicating that higher-income countries may invest in clean technology or enforce strict environmental regulations. However, at certain quantiles, the positive or negligible effect may reflect a transitional phase in which rising income initially increases environmental pressure before the adoption of clean technologies reduces it, consistent with the Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis. Trade Openness (LTO) demonstrates mixed effects across quantiles: it is positive and significant at Q0.4 and Q0.5 at the 1% level, but negative and significant at higher quantiles (Q0.7–Q0.9) at the 1% level. The environmental impact of trade openness on ecological footprint is therefore context dependent. In OIC countries with low-to-medium ecological footprints, trade integration may initially increase ecological pressure through higher production and resource use, a finding consistent with Rafique et al., 2022; Karsuh and Erkut, 2022. Conversely, in OIC nations with high ecological footprints, trade openness may facilitate access to cleaner technologies and efficiencies, resulting in a reduction in ecological footprint.

Urbanization serves as a primary source of environmental pressure on the ecological footprint across all estimated quantiles. Financial development acts as a significant moderating variable, particularly in countries with low to moderate ecological footprints. The effects of energy use, foreign direct investment (FDI), real gross domestic product (GDP), and trade openness are heterogeneous. These findings suggest that the intensity and mechanisms of their influence depend on the initial level of environmental pressure.

Conclusion and Policy Implications

This study utilizes a panel of 37 Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) countries and applies dynamic panel quantile regression to examine the relationship between ecological footprint, financial development, urbanization, and energy use, while controlling for foreign direct investment (FDI), real GDP, and trade openness from 2000 to 2024. The results underscore the importance of quantile regression, as average effects estimated using ordinary least squares (OLS), fixed effects, or random effects do not capture the heterogeneity and nonlinearities present in the data. The analysis reveals that the determinants of ecological footprint in OIC nations exert varying effects across countries. Based on these findings, several policy recommendations emerge. OIC economies should implement green financial sector reforms.

Policymakers are encouraged to strengthen financial systems by promoting environmental orientation, including the adoption of green bonds, sustainable banking practices, and climate-sensitive credit allocation. As the marginal effect of financial development diminishes at higher levels of ecological footprint, financial deepening should be accompanied by stringent environmental policies and incentives for green investment. Governments should prioritize sustainable urban development strategies, as urbanization consistently increases ecological footprint. Recommended measures include investment in mass transit, construction of energy-efficient buildings, deployment of smart city technologies, and effective waste management. Special attention is warranted for countries with mid-level ecological footprints, where the marginal environmental impact of urbanization is most pronounced. The nonlinear effects of energy consumption indicate the need for differentiated energy policies. Countries with higher ecological footprints should accelerate the transition to renewable energy, improve energy efficiency, and phase out fossil-fuel subsidies. Strengthening regulatory frameworks can help decouple energy use from environmental degradation. To mitigate the pollution haven effect, OIC countries should implement environmental screening for FDI inflows, enforce international environmental standards, and promote green and technology-driven investments.

Policy objectives should focus on maximizing the pollution-halo benefits of FDI while minimizing environmental risks. Environmental sustainability goals must align with economic growth strategies. Supporting innovation, adoption of clean technologies, and enhancing institutional quality can facilitate a transition to the declining phase of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC). Trade policies should facilitate the import of cleaner intermediate goods and environmentally friendly technologies. In high-footprint nations, deeper trade integration can serve as a tool for environmental improvement, while low- and medium-footprint countries should adopt safeguards to mitigate the ecological impacts of trade. In conclusion, environmental sustainability policies should be tailored to country-specific ecological pressures, with a focus on financial sector development, urban growth management, and the strategic use of trade integration and FDI to minimize ecological degradation.

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